

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Norqulova Jasmina Sherzod qizi

ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES AND THEIR IMPORTANCE IN TEACHING ENGLISH

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2023/IYUN

